

Relation between Charge and Stability of Colloidal Solutions of Gold and Ferric Hydroxide Dialysed to Different Extents.

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It is believed by most colloid chemists that the stability of a colloid, as determined by the coagulating concentration of an electrolyte, depends on the charge on its particles and that the greater the charge the greater will be the stability. The results of coagulation of colloids by electrolytes as well as the effect of dialysis on the stability of colloids have been explained on the basis of this view. Mukherjee, Choudhury and Rai Choudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 493) working on colloidal arsenious sulphide found that the stability is not directly related to the charge as is generally believed to be; in some of the results they found a greater stability in spite of smaller charge on the colloid. Their conclusion is however based on the results obtained with mixtures of electrolytes as well as with single electrolytes containing organic anions. It was therefore considered necessary to investigate if the same behaviour is also shown by other sols under much more simple conditions.

It is well known, that although in most cases, the stability of the sol decreases with the progress of dialysis, colloidal gold prepared by the formaldehyde method becomes more stable towards electrolytes with progress of dialysis up to a certain stage, after which stability towards electrolytes decreases (Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, English Translation, p. 506). It has also been shown by Galecki (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, **74**, 196 *et seq*) that the cataphoretic speed of gold sol increases with the progress of dialysis along with an increase in the flocculation value. In what follows results of simultaneous measurements of charge and flocculation value with potassium chloride of colloidal solutions of

gold and ferric hydroxide dialysed to different extents have been given.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of colloidal solutions.—Gold sol was prepared by Zsigmondy's nucleus method in batches of 100 c.c. Ferric hydroxide sol was prepared in instalments of 500 c.c. by adding 80 c.c. of a 45% solution of ferric chloride drop by drop to 500 c.c. of boiling distilled water; the mixture was stirred all the time and the resulting brown red sol was boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour.

The sols were transferred to parchment paper bags for dialysis. The bags were previously treated with distilled water to remove soluble matter. The outer water was changed twice a day. Suitable amounts of colloids were withdrawn every time for experiments by means of a pipette.

Method of measuring the charge.—The charge was measured according to Mukherjee's improved U-tube method (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A**, 103, 102; also Mukherjee, Choudhury and Rai Choudhury, *loc. cit.*). The electrodes were put in the side bulbs and not in the limbs of the U-tube in order to avoid the disturbing effect of electrolysis on the sharpness of the boundary.

Mukherjee, Raichoudhury and Bhattacharyya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 735) have shown that unless the upper liquid has got the same ionic composition as the intermicellary liquid the results of charge measurements are sure to be erroneous. Mukherjee, Raichoudhury and Biswas (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 375) have also shown that the use of ultrafiltrate as the upper liquid does not give reliable results. The upper liquid in our measurements of gold sol consisted of solution of potassium chloride having the same conductivity as the colloid; it gave quite satisfactory results. In the case of ferric hydroxide the upper liquid was prepared in the same manner as given by S. N. Mukherjee (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, **52**, 69).

We also performed some experiments in case of ferric hydroxide sol to see if the dialysate could be used as an upper liquid (cf. "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", *Eng. Trans.*, p. 372). It was found that in the initial stages in the case of sols dialysed for short periods and containing still appreciable amounts of HCl and FeCl₃, the dialysate obtained by keeping distilled water in contact with the colloid in the parchment bag for about 36 hours could be used as a satisfactory upper liquid. The results obtained by using the dialysate

as the upper liquid for the sol dialysed for 2 days are given below, the cataphoretic speed corrected for viscosity is expressed in centimetres per second per volt per centimetre $\times 10^5$.

TABLE I.

		Resistance of the dialysate = 66 Ohms.					
		,, ,, ,, colloid = 65 ,,					
		Potential gradient.		Direct speed.	Potential gradient.		Reverse speed.
		before cataphoresis.	after cataphoresis.		before cataphoresis.	after cataphoresis.	
Dialysate as upper liquid	(1)	0·810	0·807	35·64	0·805	0·808	36·45
	(2)	0·802	0·813	35·64	0·809	0·803	35·64

The constancy of the potential gradient as also the agreement between the upward and downward speeds with the dialysate as upper liquid is well marked and therefore evidently satisfies the requirements for uniform ionic composition. For sols dialysed for long periods, the use of the dialysate as the upper liquid did not give quite consistent values for the direct and reverse movements of the boundary, probably due to the effect of the Donnan equilibrium coming into operation. It was however found that in all cases, even for sols dialysed for long periods, the dialysate forms a very convenient liquid to start with for preparing the necessary upper liquid by adding suitable amounts of electrolytes for getting the same ionic composition as the intermicellary liquid. Further experiments to investigate fully the possibilities of the use of the dialysate as the upper liquid are in progress.

The flocculation values were determined by finding out the amount of KCl necessary for giving a definite blue colour after 5 minutes in case of gold sol and for the instantaneous precipitation of the colloid in case of colloidal ferric hydroxide, the volume of the mixture colloid + electrolyte being kept constant throughout.

The results of charge measurements and of flocculation values of gold and ferric hydroxide sols are plotted in Figures 1 and 2 respectively. The difference between the direct and reverse readings was less than 5% in each case. The concentration of the colloid did not change to any appreciable extent during dialysis.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Discussion.

From Fig. 1 it is seen that in the case of gold sol both charge (assuming that the rate of migration represents the density of the charge) and flocculation value behave similarly on subjecting the colloid to dialysis; they first increase with the progress of dialysis, reach a maximum and then begin to decrease simultaneously. In the case of ferric hydroxide sol (Fig. 2) although with the progress of dialysis the charge first increases and then decreases, the flocculation value continuously decreases.

The initial increase in charge with the progress of dialysis might be due to the following effect.

We have observed that the cataphoretic speed of colloidal gold and of ferric hydroxide first increases and then decreases on addition of small increasing amounts of KOH and of HCl and FeCl_3 respectively (unpublished results). This is due to "preferential" adsorption of the similarly charged ions in the beginning, the word "preferential" indicating that the ions are adsorbed in the inner sheet of the double layer. The amounts of stabilising ions (OH ion in case of gold sol and H and Fe ions in case of ferric hydroxide sol) in the sol continuously decreases with the progress of dialysis. The process of dialysis can be taken as the reverse of the above process, the amounts of the stabilising agent initially present in the sol being appreciably more than what will correspond to the maximum in the cataphoretic speed-concentration curve of the colloid with the particular electrolyte and therefore with the progress of dialysis the charge on the colloid will first increase and then decrease (*cf.* Freundlich, *loc. cit.*). On extreme dialysis the colloid will coagulate due to the removal of the stabilising ions from the double layer. It is therefore likely that various colloidal solutions when subjected to dialysis might show a first increase and then a decrease or a continuous decrease in the cataphoretic speed according to whether the amount of stabilising agent is more or equal to or less than what will correspond to the maximum in the cataphoretic speed-concentration curve of the sols with particular electrolytes.

The continuous decrease in the flocculation value in the case of ferric hydroxide sol, instead of an increase first and decrease thereafter as in the case of the cataphoretic speed, can be due to either or both the following effects:

(1) Rona and Michaelis (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 97, 85) have found that the amount of H ion adsorbed by charcoal was greater in the presence of potassium chloride than without it and that it reached a maximum with increasing amounts of potassium chloride (*cf.* Parks and Bartlett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 1698). Mukherjee, Choudhury and Rai Choudhury (*loc. cit.*) have found that the charge on colloidal arsenious sulphide in the presence of small amounts of an electrolyte increased on the addition of another electrolyte having a common coagulating ion but a different similarly charged ion. On the addition of KCl the colloid can be said to be under the influence of a mixture of electrolytes ($KCl + HCl + FeCl_3$) and therefore if we presume that on its addition more H and Fe ions are adsorbed in the inner sheet of the double layer, the charge on the colloid will also increase and a larger amount of potassium chloride will be required to coagulate the sol. With the progress of dialysis, the concentration of intermicellary HCl and $FeCl_3$ decreases and the charge on the particles increases. If KCl is now added the increase in the adsorption of H and Fe ions may not be so much as to raise the final charge on the particles to the value which would obtain in the case of a sol dialysed for a shorter period. (Measurements of cataphoretic speed of colloidal solution of ferric hydroxide, dialysed to different extents, in the presence of varying amounts of HCl and KCl as well as $HCl + KCl$ indicate that the adsorption of H ions does increase under certain circumstances in the presence of KCl—unpublished results.) If this be the case a smaller amount of the electrolyte will be required to coagulate the dialysed sol in spite of the higher initial charge on its particles. This mechanism will go on till the maximum in the cataphoretic speed-dialysis curve is reached. After the maximum (the portion of the curve to the right of line AB in Fig. 2) as the charge on the colloid continuously decreases with further progress of dialysis progressively smaller amounts of KCl will be required to coagulate the sol.

In the case of the gold sol the stability and charge showed a similar behaviour even during the period when the charge increased because the amount of electrolytes initially present in the intermicellary liquid (KOH and KCl) being very small, addition of KCl to the colloid may not have increased the adsorption of either or both OH and Cl ions in the inner sheet of the double layer as in the case of ferric hydroxide which contains appreciable amounts of HCl and $FeCl_3$ in the beginning. In fact we have observed that charge on

colloidal gold does not increase in the presence of small amounts of KCl as it does in the case of ferric hydroxide (unpublished results).

(2) As the charge on ferric hydroxide first increases on the addition of KCl, a greater amount of electrolyte will be required to coagulate the sol even when the charge on the colloid is initially small. We have observed that this effect becomes less marked as the purity of the colloid increases (unpublished results).

Conclusions.

From the foregoing considerations it would appear that there is nothing to warrant the view that charge and stability are not related with each other. The abnormal behaviour shown in any case can be traced to the part played by the similarly charged ions. It must, however, be pointed out at the same time that it is not safe to draw conclusions about the charge on colloidal particles from the results of stability as determined by flocculation values although in some cases flocculation values may serve a useful criterion for the same.

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